

2º filtro de seleção

Base: Scopus

Total de artigos: 34

Artigos incluídos: 25 (CI1=24, CI2=1)

Artigos excluídos: 9 (CE1=3, CE2=1, CE3=0, CE4=5, CE5=0, CE6=0)

ID	Título	Resumo	CI	CE	Motivo da exclusão
004	Multimodal conversational systems to drive the collection of patient-reported outcomes and integration into clinical workflows	Patient-reported outcomes (PROs) and their use in the clinical workflow can improve cancer survivors' outcomes and quality of life. However, there are several challenges regarding efficient collection of the patient-reported outcomes and their integration into the clinical workflow. Patient adherence and interoperability are recognized as main barriers. This work implements a cancer-related study which interconnects artificial intelligence (spoken language algorithms, conversational intelligence) and natural sciences (embodied conversational agents) to create an omni-comprehensive system enabling symmetric computer-mediated interaction. Its goal is to collect patient information and integrate it into clinical routine as digital patient resources (the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources). To further increase convenience and simplicity of the data collection, a multimodal sensing network is delivered. In this paper, we introduce the main components of the system, including the mHealth application, the Open Health Connect platform , and algorithms to deliver speech enabled 3D embodied conversational agent to interact with the cancer survivors in five different languages. The system integrates cancer patients' reported information as patient gathered health data into their digital clinical record. The value and impact of the integration will be further evaluated in the clinical study.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto.
005	Proteo: A framework for serious games in telerehabilitation	Within the context of telerehabilitation, serious games have a significant role, but creating software for serious games is resource demanding. We present Proteo, a modular and open-source framework for developing serious games from scratch. We also present two serious game implementation examples with analysis of end user and therapist/researcher satisfaction. By involving a group of 11 specialized therapists and 9 end users we analyzed the Proteo's user satisfaction. We found that both groups scored high for the level of involvement, and the therapists scored also high for the level of suitability. More in depth, both groups showed significant differences between positive and negative feelings, with positive feelings scoring higher than negative ones. Finally, the user level of suitability was reported as high while the difficulty of the system and the difficulty of the task were reported as low. Proteo has proven to be a useful tool to develop serious games for telerehabilitation and has been well accepted by the users involved in the evaluation tests.		CE4	Não foi revisado por pares (preprint).
006	Multi-domain clinical natural language processing with MedCAT: The Medical Concept Annotation Toolkit	Electronic health records (EHR) contain large volumes of unstructured text, requiring the application of information extraction (IE) technologies to enable clinical analysis. We present the open source Medical Concept Annotation Toolkit (MedCAT) that provides: (a) a novel self-supervised machine learning algorithm for extracting concepts using any concept vocabulary including UMLS/SNOMED-CT; (b) a feature-rich annotation interface for customizing and training IE models; and (c) integrations to the broader CogStack ecosystem for vendor-agnostic health system deployment. We show improved performance in extracting UMLS concepts from open datasets (F1:0.448–0.738 vs 0.429–0.650). Further real-world validation demonstrates SNOMED-CT extraction at 3 large London hospitals with self-supervised training over ~8.8B words from ~17M clinical records and further fine-tuning with ~6K clinician annotated examples. We show strong transferability (F1 > 0.94) between hospitals, datasets and concept types indicating cross-domain EHR-agnostic utility for accelerated clinical and research use cases.	CI1		
021	Immunization calculation engine: An open source immunization evaluation and forecasting system	Introduction: The immunization calculation engine (ICE) is a free, open-source immunization forecasting evaluation and software system whose default immunization schedule supports all routine childhood, adolescent, and adult immunizations based on the recommendations of the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices (ACIP). ICE utilizes its immunization rules and patient data to evaluate and return the validity of each immunization in the patient's history	CI1		

		<p>along with one or more evaluation reasons. It also returns a recommendation for each vaccine group along with one or more recommendation reasons. Methods: In January 2020, ICE was first released as a Docker image along with the traditional zip archive file which had been used up to that point. Docker enables software providers to easily distribute their software so that it can be run “out of the box” in the user's local environment. Software running in Docker containers drastically reduces the complexity of software distribution and set up. Results: Clinical systems of many types use ICE. The project began within the public health arena as a feature of Immunization Information Systems (IIS), but electronic health records (EHR) and personal health records (PHR) have also deployed ICE. While it is not possible to identify the specific impact of ICE on clinical care without additional research, it should be pointed out that once deployed within an IIS, EHR, or PHR the display of ICE results is performed for every patient viewed by a user and often for every patient appearing on a report. In a typical month, thousands if not millions of evaluations and forecasts are performed by ICE and displayed to the users. Conclusions: The ICE Project believes in minimizing the barriers to installing and using ICE anywhere. To that end, there is no registration required to download the source code or runtime code for the ICE service and its default rule. Similarly, the Project created a Docker image of ICE to facilitate easy and seamless implementation.</p>			
028	<p>Epidemiologic evolution platform using integrated modeling and geographic information system</p>	<p>At the international level, a major effort is being made to optimize the flow of data and information for health systems management. The studies show that medical and economic efficiency is strongly influenced by the level of development and complexity of implementing an integrated system of epidemiological monitoring and modeling. The solution proposed and described in this paper is addressed to all public and private institutions involved in the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic, using recognized methods and standards in this field. The Green-Epidemio is a platform adaptable to the specific features of any public institution for disease management, based on open-source software, allowing the adaptation, customization, and further development of "open-source" applications, according to the specificities of the public institution, the changes in the economic and social environment and its legal framework. The platform has a mathematical model for the spread of COVID-19 infection depending on the location of the outbreaks so that the allocation of resources and the geographical limitation of certain areas can be parameterized according to the number and location of the real-time identified outbreaks. The social impact of the proposed solution is due to the planned applications of information flow management, which is a first step in improving significantly the response time and efficiency of people-operated response services. Moreover, institutional interoperability influences strategic societal factors.</p>	CI1		
039	<p>Handling missing data in modelling quality of clinician-prescribed routine care: Sensitivity analysis of departure from missing at random assumption</p>	<p>Missing information is a major drawback in analyzing data collected in many routine health care settings. Multiple imputation assuming a missing at random mechanism is a popular method to handle missing data. The missing at random assumption cannot be confirmed from the observed data alone, hence the need for sensitivity analysis to assess robustness of inference. However, sensitivity analysis is rarely conducted and reported in practice. We analyzed routine paediatric data collected during a cluster randomized trial conducted in Kenyan hospitals. We imputed missing patient and clinician-level variables assuming the missing at random mechanism. We also imputed missing clinician-level variables assuming a missing not at random mechanism. We incorporated opinions from 15 clinical experts in the form of prior distributions and shift parameters in the delta adjustment method. An interaction between trial intervention arm and follow-up time, hospital, clinician and patient-level factors were included in a proportional odds random-effects analysis model. We performed these analyses using R functions derived from the jomo package. Parameter estimates from multiple imputation under the missing at random mechanism were similar to multiple imputation estimates assuming the missing not at random mechanism. Our inferences were insensitive to departures from the missing at random assumption using either the prior distributions or shift parameters sensitivity analysis approach.</p>		CE2	<p>Não está disponível integralmente/gratuitamente.</p>

040	<p>Collaborative Cloud Computing Framework for Health Data with Open Source Technologies</p>	<p>The proliferation of sensor technologies and advancements in data collection methods have enabled the accumulation of very large amounts of data. Increasingly, these datasets are considered for scientific research. However, the design of the system architecture to achieve high performance in terms of parallelization, query processing time, aggregation of heterogeneous data types (e.g., time series, images, structured data, among others), and difficulty in reproducing scientific research remain a major challenge. This is specifically true for health sciences research, where the systems must be i) easy to use with the flexibility to manipulate data at the most granular level, ii) agnostic of programming language kernel, iii) scalable, and iv) compliant with the HIPAA privacy law. In this paper, we review the existing literature for such big data systems for scientific research in health sciences and identify the gaps of the current system landscape. We propose a novel architecture for software-hardware-data ecosystem using open source technologies such as Apache Hadoop, Kubernetes and JupyterHub in a distributed environment. We also evaluate the system using a large clinical data set of 69M patients.</p>	CI1		
043	<p>COVID-19 scenario modelling for the mitigation of capacity-dependent deaths in intensive care</p>	<p>Managing healthcare demand and capacity is especially difficult in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, where limited intensive care resources can be overwhelmed by a large number of cases requiring admission in a short space of time. If patients are unable to access this specialist resource, then death is a likely outcome. In appreciating these ‘capacity-dependent’ deaths, this paper reports on the clinically-led development of a stochastic discrete event simulation model designed to capture the key dynamics of the intensive care admissions process for COVID-19 patients. With application to a large public hospital in England during an early stage of the pandemic, the purpose of this study was to estimate the extent to which such capacity-dependent deaths can be mitigated through demand-side initiatives involving non-pharmaceutical interventions and supply-side measures to increase surge capacity. Based on information available at the time, results suggest that total capacity-dependent deaths can be reduced by 75% through a combination of increasing capacity from 45 to 100 beds, reducing length of stay by 25%, and flattening the peak demand to 26 admissions per day. Accounting for the additional ‘capacity-independent’ deaths, which occur even when appropriate care is available within the intensive care setting, yields an aggregate reduction in total deaths of 30%. The modelling tool, which is freely available and open source, has since been used to support COVID-19 response planning at a number of healthcare systems within the UK National Health Service.</p>	CI1		
052	<p>Enabling agile clinical and translational data warehousing Platform development and evaluation</p>	<p>Background: Modern data-driven medical research provides new insights into the development and course of diseases and enables novel methods of clinical decision support. Clinical and translational data warehouses, such as Informatics for Integrating Biology and the Bedside (i2b2) and tranSMART, are important infrastructure components that provide users with unified access to the large heterogeneous data sets needed to realize this and support use cases such as cohort selection, hypothesis generation, and ad hoc data analysis. Objective: Often, different warehousing platforms are needed to support different use cases and different types of data. Moreover, to achieve an optimal data representation within the target systems, specific domain knowledge is needed when designing data-loading processes. Consequently, informaticians need to work closely with clinicians and researchers in short iterations. This is a challenging task as installing and maintaining warehousing platforms can be complex and time consuming. Furthermore, data loading typically requires significant effort in terms of data preprocessing, cleansing, and restructuring. The platform described in this study aims to address these challenges. Methods: We formulated system requirements to achieve agility in terms of platform management and data loading. The derived system architecture includes a cloud infrastructure with unified management interfaces for multiple warehouse platforms and a data-loading pipeline with a declarative configuration paradigm and meta-loading approach. The latter compiles data and configuration files into forms required by existing loading tools, thereby automating a wide range of data restructuring and cleansing tasks. We demonstrated the fulfillment of the requirements and the originality of our approach by an experimental evaluation and a comparison with previous work. Results: The platform supports both i2b2 and tranSMART with built-in security. Our experiments</p>	CE4	Dissertaçã o.	

		<p>showed that the loading pipeline accepts input data that cannot be loaded with existing tools without preprocessing. Moreover, it lowered efforts significantly, reducing the size of configuration files required by factors of up to 22 for tranSMART and 1135 for i2b2. The time required to perform the compilation process was roughly equivalent to the time required for actual data loading. Comparison with other tools showed that our solution was the only tool fulfilling all requirements. Conclusions: Our platform significantly reduces the efforts required for managing clinical and translational warehouses and for loading data in various formats and structures, such as complex entity-attribute-value structures often found in laboratory data. Moreover, it facilitates the iterative refinement of data representations in the target platforms, as the required configuration files are very compact. The quantitative measurements presented are consistent with our experiences of significantly reduced efforts for building warehousing platforms in close cooperation with medical researchers. Both the cloud-based hosting infrastructure and the data-loading pipeline are available to the community as open source software with comprehensive documentation.</p>			
082	<p>FOSS TECHNOLOGIES IN MODELLING SPATIAL ACCESSIBILITY OF PRIMARY HEALTH CARE IN MALAWI</p>	<p>Primary health care (PHC) is the first point of contact people have with a health system. As such access to PHC services is an important factor to ensure good health of a community. While the need to provide equal and easy access to PHC is well understood, the approaches informing the decision-making process to improve the access tend to face a number of challenges in the developing world. Use of conventional Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) comes with requisite financial costs which Free and Open Source Software (FOSS) ICT technologies have the potential to help lower among other benefits. In this study, the confluence of spatial accessibility tools provided by FOSS technologies, specifically PostgreSQL/PostGIS and QGIS, was explored to inform decision making in PHC accessibility in Zomba, Malawi. The results show that the household population (P) that is within the threshold time was 82,863, representing 59% of all households having access to health care. The mean accessibility score for the district was 0.010 and ranged from 0.00 to 0.231. While the findings provide, arguably, spatially objective PHC accessibility data to inform policy direction and also reveals accessibility to PHC in Malawi to be lower than reported, the study also reveals the usefulness of FOSS technologies, in the developing world. Use of FOSS facilitated incremental setup of the model thereby allowing to run the model with limited processing power. That notwithstanding, the study adds to the formal scientific research on the use of relational spatial analysis in the developing world.</p>	CI1		
088	<p>Supporting integrated care with a flexible data management framework built upon Linked Data, HL7 FHIR and ontologies</p>	<p>In this paper we present the methodology and decisions behind an implementation of a telehealth data management framework, aiming to support integrated care services for chronic and multimorbid patients. The framework leverages an OWL ontology, built upon HL7 FHIR resources, to provide storage and representation of semantically enriched EHR data following Linked Data principles. This is presented along with the realization of the persistent storage solution and communication web services that allow the management of EHR data, ensuring the validity and integrity of the exchanged patient data as self-describing ontology instances. The framework concentrates on flexibility and reusability, which is addressed by regarding the aforementioned ontology as a single point of change. This solution has been implemented in the scope of the EU project WELCOME for managing data in a telemonitoring system for patients with COPD and co-morbidities and was also successfully deployed for the INLIFE EU project with minimal effort. The results of the two applications suggest it can be adopted and properly adapted in a series of integrated care scenarios with minimal effort.</p>	CI1		
089	<p>Design and virtual implementation of a biomedical registry framework for the enhancement</p>	<p>Introduction Clinical trials generate a large volume of literature and a vast amount of data. Following the 'open science' model, data sharing has enormous potential to strengthen scientific research. Currently, to the best of our knowledge, there is no existing web based Hellenic biomedical registry that displays available patients for clinical trials, providing direct access to registered physicians to all data, assisting them in finding eligible patients in the initial clinical trial recruitment process. Methods This paper describes the design and virtual implementation of a web based prototype biomedical registry in Greece. The system represents an eGovernment framework proposal for the central storage of patients' biomedical information and</p>	CI1		

	of clinical trials: colorectal cancer example	the operations associated with this process. The increasing tendency to include molecular data as prerequisite elements in clinical trials is adopted in the registry philosophy. The designed system is based on free, open source software and it is implemented virtually on a local host environment. Results Using colorectal cancer as an example, valid data from patients increases the reliability index, demonstrating the functionality of the web application. Conclusion In conclusion, the combination of biomedical data and information technology in order to display potential participants per health unit, facilitates recruitment for clinical trials.			
098	Securing web applications through a framework of source code analysis	Source code analysis is becoming extremely important for the universal acceptance of web applications because the automated source code analysis tools play a key role in identifying and fixing security-related vulnerabilities. This paper proposes a framework for securing web applications through source code analysis. The framework has three prescriptive phases including executing and monitoring, classifying and controlling and refining and managing. The framework helps to examine the web application source code related to security issues. The executing and monitoring phase employs five different open source tools for statically analyzing the source code. According to the literature, there are nine broad categories of vulnerabilities in web applications. After filtration of these vulnerabilities, classifying and controlling phase categorize the vulnerabilities according to their severity level with the help of fuzzy analytical analysis process and suggestive measures. The refining and managing phase takes these measures and suggests changes to the source code to make it more secure. This framework was validated through a web-based hospital management system. The results of the validation showed that the framework implementation made the source code more robust towards the upcoming vulnerabilities and bugs.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
104	Automated gathering and analysis of cannabinoids treatment data	The paper presents an open source platform to integrate and analyse the cannabinoids research data gathered from academic publications, industrial and clinical trials as well as patients. The project focuses on the analysis of the usability aspects important for the applications collecting the treatment data as well as data on diverse cannabinoids strains. The collected data will be used to estimate the efficiency of cannabinoid treatment of various disorders, which will provide an evidence-based assistance for doctors, researchers and industry to identify the right cannabinoid profiles for various conditions.	CII		
124	Implementing an open source electronic health record system in kenyan health care facilities: Case study	Background: The Kenyan government, working with international partners and local organizations, has developed an eHealth strategy, specified standards, and guidelines for electronic health record adoption in public hospitals and implemented two major health information technology projects: District Health Information Software Version 2, for collating national health care indicators and a rollout of the KenyaEMR and International Quality Care Health Management Information Systems, for managing 600 HIV clinics across the country. Following these projects, a modified version of the Open Medical Record System electronic health record was specified and developed to fulfill the clinical and administrative requirements of health care facilities operated by devolved counties in Kenya and to automate the process of collating health care indicators and entering them into the District Health Information Software Version 2 system. Objective: We aimed to present a descriptive case study of the implementation of an open source electronic health record system in public health care facilities in Kenya. Methods: We conducted a landscape review of existing literature concerning eHealth policies and electronic health record development in Kenya. Following initial discussions with the Ministry of Health, the World Health Organization, and implementing partners, we conducted a series of visits to implementing sites to conduct semistructured individual interviews and group discussions with stakeholders to produce a historical case study of the implementation. Results: This case study describes how consultants based in Kenya, working with developers in India and project stakeholders, implemented the new system into several public hospitals in a county in rural Kenya. The implementation process included upgrading the hospital information technology infrastructure, training users, and attempting to garner administrative and clinical buy-in for adoption of the system. The initial deployment was ultimately scaled back due to a complex mix of sociotechnical and administrative issues. Learning from these early challenges, the system is now being		CE4	Capítulo de livro.

		redesigned and prepared for deployment in 6 new counties across Kenya. Conclusions: Implementing electronic health record systems is a challenging process in high-income settings. In low-income settings, such as Kenya, open source software may offer some respite from the high costs of software licensing, but the familiar challenges of clinical and administration buy-in, the need to adequately train users, and the need for the provision of ongoing technical support are common across the North-South divide. Strategies such as creating local support teams, using local development resources, ensuring end user buy-in, and rolling out in smaller facilities before larger hospitals are being incorporated into the project. These are positive developments to help maintain momentum as the project continues. Further integration with existing open source communities could help ongoing development and implementations of the project. We hope this case study will provide some lessons and guidance for other challenging implementations of electronic health record systems as they continue across Africa.			
133	Combining Ontologies and Open Standards to Derive a Middle Layer Information Model for Interoperability of Personal and Electronic Health Records	The aim of our study was to enable better interoperability between Personal Health Record (PHR) and Electronic Health Record (EHR) systems and vice versa. A multi-layer architectural model that resides between a PHR and EHR system has been developed. The model consists of an ontology-driven information model and a set of transformation rules that work in conjunction to process data exported from a PHR or EHR system and prepare it accordingly for the receiving system. The model was evaluated by executing a set of case study scenarios containing data from both a PHR and an EHR system. This allowed various challenges to emerge and revealed gaps in current standards in use. The proposed information model offers a number of advantages. Altering only the information model can incorporate modifications to either a PHR or EHR system. The model uses classes and attributes to define how data is captured which allows greater flexibility in how data can be manipulated by receiving systems.	CI1		
135	eWALL: An Open-Source Cloud-Based eHealth Platform for Creating Home-Caring Environments for Older Adults Living with Chronic Diseases or Frailty	Independent living of older adults is one of the main challenges linked to the ageing population. Especially those living with diseases like COPD, MCI or frailty, need more support in everyday life and this is by itself a big societal challenge with impact in multiple sectors. In this paper we present eWALL, an innovative open-source eHealth platform that aims to address these challenges by means of an advanced cloud-based infrastructure. eWALL is designed in an innovative manner and achieved technical breakthroughs in eHealth platforms, while prioritizing user and market needs that are often abandoned and are the major reason for technically sound solutions that fail. We consider this as an opportunity and we aim to change the eHealth systems' experience for older adults and break the barriers for the penetration of ICT solutions.	CI1		
150	VDIML: A file format with tools for capturing the results of inferring immune receptor rearrangements	Background: The genes that produce antibodies and the immune receptors expressed on lymphocytes are not germline encoded; rather, they are somatically generated in each developing lymphocyte by a process called V(D)J recombination, which assembles specific, independent gene segments into mature composite genes. The full set of composite genes in an individual at a single point in time is referred to as the immune repertoire. V(D)J recombination is the distinguishing feature of adaptive immunity and enables effective immune responses against an essentially infinite array of antigens. Characterization of immune repertoires is critical in both basic research and clinical contexts. Recent technological advances in repertoire profiling via high-throughput sequencing have resulted in an explosion of research activity in the field. This has been accompanied by a proliferation of software tools for analysis of repertoire sequencing data. Despite the widespread use of immune repertoire profiling and analysis software, there is currently no standardized format for output files from V(D)J analysis. Researchers utilize software such as IgBLAST and IMGT/High V-QUEST to perform V(D)J analysis and infer the structure of germline rearrangements. However, each of these software tools produces results in a different file format, and can annotate the same result using different labels. These differences make it challenging for users to perform additional downstream analyses. Results: To help address this problem, we propose a standardized file	CI1		

		format for representing V(D)J analysis results. The proposed format, VDJML, provides a common standardized format for different V(D)J analysis applications to facilitate downstream processing of the results in an application-agnostic manner. The VDJML file format specification is accompanied by a support library, written in C++ and Python, for reading and writing the VDJML file format. Conclusions: The VDJML suite will allow users to streamline their V(D)J analysis and facilitate the sharing of scientific knowledge within the community. The VDJML suite and documentation are available from https://vdjserver.org/vdjml/ . We welcome participation from the community in developing the file format standard, as well as code contributions.			
151	WaveformECG: A platform for visualizing, annotating, and analyzing ECG data	The electrocardiogram (ECG) is the most commonly collected data in cardiovascular research because of the ease with which it can be measured and the fact that changes in ECG waveforms reflect underlying aspects of heart disease. Despite its ubiquity, there are no open, noncommercial platforms for interactive management, sharing, and analysis of these data. WaveformECG addresses this unmet need. Accessed through a browser, WaveformECG extracts ECGs from vendor files, storing them as a time series with other analysis results and annotations in an open source time-series database . It supports interactive invocation of multiple analysis algorithms on selected ECG datasets, visualization of ECG waveforms, manual annotation of time points and intervals in ECG waveforms, and automated annotation of analysis results using standard medical terminology. Integration with the I2B2 clinical data warehouse system enables bidirectional exchange of data between these two platforms.	CII		
153	The Apollo Structured Vocabulary: An OWL2 ontology of phenomena in infectious disease epidemiology and population biology for use in epidemic simulation	Background: We developed the Apollo Structured Vocabulary (Apollo-SV)-an OWL2 ontology of phenomena in infectious disease epidemiology and population biology-as part of a project whose goal is to increase the use of epidemic simulators in public health practice. Apollo-SV defines a terminology for use in simulator configuration. Apollo-SV is the product of an ontological analysis of the domain of infectious disease epidemiology, with particular attention to the inputs and outputs of nine simulators. Results: Apollo-SV contains 802 classes for representing the inputs and outputs of simulators, of which approximately half are new and half are imported from existing ontologies. The most important Apollo-SV class for users of simulators is infectious disease scenario, which is a representation of an ecosystem at simulator time zero that has at least one infection process (a class) affecting at least one population (also a class). Other important classes represent ecosystem elements (e.g., households), ecosystem processes (e.g., infection acquisition and infectious disease), censuses of ecosystem elements (e.g., censuses of populations), and infectious disease control measures. In the larger project, which created an end-user application that can send the same infectious disease scenario to multiple simulators, Apollo-SV serves as the controlled terminology and strongly influences the design of the message syntax used to represent an infectious disease scenario. As we added simulators for different pathogens (e.g., malaria and dengue), the core classes of Apollo-SV have remained stable, suggesting that our conceptualization of the information required by simulators is sound. Despite adhering to the OBO Foundry principle of orthogonality, we could not reuse Infectious Disease Ontology classes as the basis for infectious disease scenarios. We thus defined new classes in Apollo-SV for host, pathogen, infection, infectious disease, colonization, and infection acquisition. Unlike IDO, our ontological analysis extended to existing mathematical models of key biological phenomena studied by infectious disease epidemiology and population biology. Conclusion: Our ontological analysis as expressed in Apollo-SV was instrumental in developing a simulator-independent representation of infectious disease scenarios that can be run on multiple epidemic simulators. Our experience suggests the importance of extending ontological analysis of a domain to include existing mathematical models of the phenomena studied by the domain. Apollo-SV is freely available at: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/apollo_sv.owl	CII		
155	An ontological model of the	Patient-centered medical home is defined as an approach for providing comprehensive primary care that facilitates partnerships between individual patients and their personal providers. The current state of the practice transformation process is ad hoc and no methodological basis exists for transforming a practice into a	CII		

	<p>practice transformation process</p>	<p>patient-centered medical home. Practices and hospitals somehow accomplish the transformation and send the transformation information to a certification agency, such as the National Committee for Quality Assurance, completely ignoring the development and maintenance of the processes that keep the medical home concept alive. Many recent studies point out that such a transformation is hard as it requires an ambitious whole-practice reengineering and redesign. As a result, the practices suffer change fatigue in getting the transformation done. In this paper, we focus on the complexities of the practice transformation process and present a robust ontological model for practice transformation. The objective of the model is to create an understanding of the practice transformation process in terms of key process areas and their activities. We describe how our ontology captures the knowledge of the practice transformation process, elicited from domain experts, and also discuss how, in the future, that knowledge could be diffused across stakeholders in a healthcare organization. Our research is the first effort in practice transformation process modeling. To build an ontological model for practice transformation, we adopt the Methontology approach. Based on the literature, we first identify the key process areas essential for a practice transformation process to achieve certification status. Next, we develop the practice transformation ontology by creating key activities and precedence relationships among the key process areas using process maturity concepts. At each step, we employ a panel of domain experts to verify the intermediate representations of the ontology. Finally, we implement a prototype of the practice transformation ontology using Protégé</p>			
156	<p>Anatomy of an Extensible Open Source PACS</p>	<p>The conception and deployment of cost effective Picture Archiving and Communication Systems (PACS) is a concern for small to medium medical imaging facilities, research environments, and developing countries' healthcare institutions. Financial constraints and the specificity of these scenarios contribute to a low adoption rate of PACS in those environments. Furthermore, with the advent of ubiquitous computing and new initiatives to improve healthcare information technologies and data sharing, such as IHE and XDS-i, a PACS must adapt quickly to changes. This paper describes Dicoogle, a software framework that enables developers and researchers to quickly prototype and deploy new functionality taking advantage of the embedded Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) services. This full-fledged implementation of a PACS archive is very amenable to extension due to its plugin-based architecture and out-of-the-box functionality, which enables the exploration of large DICOM datasets and associated metadata. These characteristics make the proposed solution very interesting for prototyping, experimentation, and bridging functionality with deployed applications. Besides being an advanced mechanism for data discovery and retrieval based on DICOM object indexing, it enables the detection of inconsistencies in an institution's data and processes. Several use cases have benefited from this approach such as radiation dosage monitoring, Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR), and the use of the framework as support for classes targeting software engineering for clinical contexts.</p>	CII		
163	<p>Integrating genomic resources with electronic health records using the HL7 infobutton standard</p>	<p>Background: The Clinical Genome Resource (ClinGen) Electronic Health Record (EHR) Workgroup aims to integrate ClinGen resources with EHRs. A promising option to enable this integration is through the Health Level Seven (HL7) Infobutton Standard. EHR systems that are certified according to the US Meaningful Use program provide HL7-compliant infobutton capabilities, which can be leveraged to support clinical decision-making in genomics. Objectives: To integrate genomic knowledge resources using the HL7 infobutton standard. Two tactics to achieve this objective were: (1) creating an HL7-compliant search interface for ClinGen, and (2) proposing guidance for genomic resources on achieving HL7 Infobutton standard accessibility and compliance. Methods: We built a search interface utilizing OpenInfobutton, an open source reference implementation of the HL7 Infobutton standard. ClinGen resources were assessed for readiness towards HL7 compliance. Finally, based upon our experiences we provide recommendations for publishers seeking to achieve HL7 compliance. Results: Eight genomic resources and two sub-resources were integrated with the ClinGen search engine via OpenInfobutton and the HL7 infobutton standard. Resources we assessed have varying levels of readiness towards HL7-compliance. Furthermore, we found that</p>	CII		

		adoption of standard terminologies used by EHR systems is the main gap to achieve compliance. Conclusion: Genomic resources can be integrated with EHR systems via the HL7 Infobutton standard using OpenInfobutton. Full compliance of genomic resources with the Infobutton standard would further enhance interoperability with EHR systems.			
171	An adaptive case management system to support integrated care services: Lessons learned from the NEXES project	Background: Extensive deployment and sustainability of integrated care services (ICS) constitute an unmet need to reduce the burden of chronic conditions. The European Union project NEXES (2008-2013) assessed the deployment of four ICS encompassing the spectrum of severity of chronic patients. Objective: The current study aims to (i) describe the open source Adaptive Case Management (ACM) system (Linkcare®) developed to support the deployment of ICS at the level of healthcare district; (ii) to evaluate its performance; and, (iii) to identify key challenges for regional deployment of ICS. Methods: We first defined a conceptual model for ICS management and execution composed of five main stages. We then specified an associated logical model considering the dynamic runtime of ACM. Finally, we implemented the four ICS as a physical model with an ICS editor to allow professionals (case managers) to play active roles in adapting the system to their needs. Instances of ICS were then run in Linkcare®. Four ICS provided a framework for evaluating the system: Wellness and Rehabilitation (W&R) (number of patients enrolled in the study (n) =. 173); Enhanced Care (EC) in frail chronic patients to prevent hospital admissions, (n=. 848); Home Hospitalization and Early Discharge (HH/ED) (n=. 2314); and, Support to remote diagnosis (Support) (n=. 7793). The method for assessment of telemedicine applications (MAST) was used for iterative evaluation. Results: Linkcare® supports ACM with shared-care plans across healthcare tiers and offers integration with provider-specific electronic health records. Linkcare® successfully contributed to the deployment of the four ICS: W&R facilitated long-term sustainability of training effects (p<. 0.01) and active life style (p<. 0.03); EC showed significant positive outcomes (p<. 0.05); HH/ED reduced on average 5 in-hospital days per patient with a 30-d re-admission rate of 10%; and, Support, enhanced community-based quality forced spirometry testing (p<. 0.01). Key challenges for regional deployment of personalized care were identified. Conclusions: Linkcare® provided the required functionalities to support integrated care adopting an ACM model, and it showed adaptive potential for its implementation in different health scenarios. The research generated strategies that contributed to face the challenges of the transition toward personalized medicine for chronic patients.	CII		
175	Ontological modeling of electronic health information exchange	Introduction: Investments of resources to purposively improve the movement of information between health system providers are currently made with imperfect information. No inventories of system-level electronic health information flows currently exist, nor do measures of inter-organizational electronic information exchange. Methods: Using Protégé 4, an open-source OWL Web ontology language editor and knowledge-based framework, we formalized a model that decomposes inter-organizational electronic health information flow into derivative concepts such as diversity, breadth, volume, structure, standardization and connectivity. Results: The ontology was populated with data from a regional health system and the flows were measured. Individual instance's properties were inferred from their class associations as determined by their data and object property rules. It was also possible to visualize interoperability activity for regional analysis and planning purposes. A property called Impact was created from the total number of patients or clients that a health entity in the region served in a year, and the total number of health service providers or organizations with whom it exchanged information in support of clinical decision-making, diagnosis or treatment. Identifying providers with a high Impact but low Interoperability score could assist planners and policy-makers to optimize technology investments intended to electronically share patient information across the continuum of care. Finally, we demonstrated how linked ontologies were used to identify logical inconsistencies in self-reported data for the study.	CII		

176	KenVACS: Improving vaccination of children through cellular network technology in developing countries	Health Data collection is one of the major components of public health systems. Decision makers, policy makers, and medical service providers need accurate and timely data in order to improve the quality of health services. The rapid growth and use of mobile technologies has exerted pressure on the demand for mobile-based data collection solutions to bridge the information gaps in the health sector. We propose a prototype using open source data collection frameworks to test its feasibility in improving the vaccination data collection in Kenya. KenVACS, the proposed prototype, offers ways of collecting vaccination data through mobile phones and visualizes the collected data in a web application; the system also sends reminder short messages service (SMS) to remind parents on the date of the next vaccination. Early evaluation demonstrates the benefits of such a system in supporting and improving vaccination of children. Finally, we conducted a qualitative study to assess challenges in remote health data collection and evaluated usability and functionality of KenVACS.	CI1		
181	Modern framework for distributed healthcare data analytics based on hadoop	Evolution in the field of IT, electronics and networking resulted in enhancements in connectivity and in computation capabilities. Proliferation of miniaturized devices paved way for Body Area Network. Healthcare systems have been going through cycles of modernization as the advent of IT system in the field of medical sciences. Body Area Network is a network of lightweight wearable sensor nodes that sense human body functions. Modern healthcare informatics systems produce lots of data that emerge from sensors. Even though many healthcare informatics systems exist and produce volume of data, such solutions exist in silos. Existing Healthcare IT systems intend to gather multivariate medical data about the patients by the means of electronic format. They capture multi variant types of data, process and store them in a RDBMS. Inferring knowledge from such systems is tedious. This paper aims at proposing a framework for modernizing the healthcare informatics systems. Proposed framework is based on Apache Hadoop platform which is open source and its implementation is distributed in nature as it is deployable at various healthcare centers in different geographic locations.	CI1		
182	Community-based early warning and adaptive response system (EWARS) for mosquito borne diseases: An open source/open community approach	A variety of studies around the world have evaluated the use of remote sensing with and without GIS in communicable diseases. The ongoing Ebola epidemic has highlighted the risks that can arise for the global community from rapidly spreading diseases which may outpace attempts at control and eradication. This paper presents an approach to the development, deployment, validation and wide-spread adoption of a GIS-based temporo-spatial decision support system which is being collaboratively developed in open source/open community mode by an international group that came together under UN auspices. The group believes in an open source/open community approach to make the fruits of knowledge as widely accessible as possible. A core initiative of the groups is the EWARS project. It proposes to strengthen existing public health systems by the development and validation a model for a community based surveillance and response system which will initially address mosquito borne diseases in the developing world. At present mathematical modeling to support EWARS is at an advanced state, and it planned to embark on a pilot project.		CE4	Relatório.
194	The Analytic Information Warehouse (AIW): A platform for analytics using electronic health record data	Objective: To create an analytics platform for specifying and detecting clinical phenotypes and other derived variables in electronic health record (EHR) data for quality improvement investigations. Materials and methods: We have developed an architecture for an Analytic Information Warehouse (AIW). It supports transforming data represented in different physical schemas into a common data model, specifying derived variables in terms of the common model to enable their reuse, computing derived variables while enforcing invariants and ensuring correctness and consistency of data transformations, long-term curation of derived data, and export of derived data into standard analysis tools. It includes software that implements these features and a computing environment that enables secure high-performance access to and processing of large datasets extracted from EHRs. Results: We have implemented and deployed the architecture in production locally. The software is available as open source. We have used it as part of hospital operations in a project to reduce rates of hospital readmission within 30. days. The project examined the association of over 100 derived variables representing disease and co-morbidity phenotypes with readmissions in 5. years of data from our	CI1		

		institution's clinical data warehouse and the UHC Clinical Database (CDB). The CDB contains administrative data from over 200 hospitals that are in academic medical centers or affiliated with such centers. Discussion and conclusion: A widely available platform for managing and detecting phenotypes in EHR data could accelerate the use of such data in quality improvement and comparative effectiveness studies.			
200	A software tool for large-scale sharing and querying of clinical documents modeled using HL7 version 3 standard	We present a novel software tool called CDN (Collaborative Data Network) for large-scale sharing and querying of clinical documents modeled using HL7 v3 standard (e.g., Clinical Document Architecture (CDA), Continuity of Care Document (CCD)). Similar to the caBIG initiative, CDN aims to foster innovations in cancer treatment and diagnosis through large-scale, sharing of clinical data. We focus on cancer because it is the second leading cause of deaths in the US. CDN is based on the synergistic combination of peer-to-peer technology and the extensible markup language XML and XQuery. Using CDN, a user can pose both structured queries and keyword queries on the HL7 v3 documents hosted by data providers. CDN is unique in its design - it supports location oblivious queries in a large-scale, network wherein a user does not explicitly provide the location of the data for a query. A location service in CDN discovers data of interest in the network at query time. CDN uses standard cryptographic techniques to provide security to data providers and protect the privacy of patients. Using CDN, a user can pose clinical queries pertaining to cancer containing aggregations and joins across data hosted by multiple data providers. CDN is implemented with open-source software for web application development and XML query processing. We report the evaluation of CDN in a distributed environment (LAN) using a real dataset of discharge summaries available from the i2b2 project.	CII		
209	Prototyping closed loop physiologic control with the medical device coordination framework	Medical devices historically have been monolithic units - developed, validated, and approved by regulatory authorities as standalone entities. Despite the fact that modern medical devices increasingly incorporate connectivity mechanisms that enable device data to be streamed to electronic health records and displays that aggregate data from multiple devices, connectivity is not being leveraged to allow an integrated collection of devices to work together as a single system to automate clinical work flows. This is due, in part, to current regulatory policies which prohibit such interactions due to safety concerns. In previous work, we proposed an open source middleware framework and an accompanying model-based development environment that could be used to quickly implement medical device coordination applications - enabling a "systems of systems" paradigm for medical devices. Such a paradigm shows great promise for supporting many applications that increase both the safety and effectiveness of medical care as well as the efficiency of clinical workflows. In this paper, we report on our experience using our Medical Device Coordination Framework (MDCF) to carry out a rapid prototyping of one such application - a multi-device medical system that uses closed loop physiologic control to affect better patient outcomes for Patient Controlled Analgesic (PCA) pumps.		CEI	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
211	Medicare-grid: New trends on the development of E-health system based on grid technology	The evolution of information technology over the last decade has brought opportunities to improvements in the state of art of medical services. One scenario is that a patient's digital health record can easily be shared among hospitals and medical centers via internet, enabling the examination performed in one location while clinical diagnosis be done by physicians in another. In this paper, we propose a Medicare-Grid — a novel grid-based E-health system proposed to ease the process of retrieving and exchanging personal health data among hospitals and medical centers. Grid and peer-to-peer technologies have been used to integrate computing and storage resources provided by hospitals, as also to develop an Electronic Health Record (EHR) center to store and share EHRs among these locations. We have also developed a system prototype using ultimate hardware resources and open source software systems to simulate a real scenario as described above. We demonstrate that the idea proposed in the project is feasible, possible to be implemented and applicable to real world.	CII		

217	<p>Open source GIS for HIV/AIDS management</p>	<p>Background: Reliable access to basic services can improve a community's resilience to HIV/AIDS. Accordingly, work is being done to upgrade the physical infrastructure in affected areas, often employing a strategy of decentralised service provision. Spatial characteristics are one of the major determinants in implementing services, even in the smaller municipal areas, and good quality spatial information is needed to inform decision making processes. However, limited funds, technical infrastructure and human resource capacity result in little or no access to spatial information for crucial infrastructure development decisions at local level. This research investigated whether it would be possible to develop a GIS for basic infrastructure planning and management at local level. Given the resource constraints of the local government context, particularly in small municipalities, it was decided that open source software should be used for the prototype system. Results: The design and development of a prototype system illustrated that it is possible to develop an open source GIS system that can be used within the context of local information management. Usability tests show a high degree of usability for the system, which is important considering the heavy workload and high staff turnover that characterises local government in South Africa. Local infrastructure management stakeholders interviewed in a case study of a South African municipality see the potential for the use of GIS as a communication tool and are generally positive about the use of GIS for these purposes. They note security issues that may arise through the sharing of information, lack of skills and resource constraints as the major barriers to adoption. Conclusion: The case study shows that spatial information is an identified need at local level. Open source GIS software can be used to develop a system to provide local-level stakeholders with spatial information. However, the suitability of the technology is only a part of the system - there are wider information and management issues which need to be addressed before the implementation of a local-level GIS for infrastructure management can be successful.</p>	CI2		
218	<p>Work in progress: Exploring security and privacy concepts through the development and testing of the iTrust medical records system</p>	<p>University computer science and software engineering students must build reliability and security into their software applications from the start of development. A graduate-level Software Testing and Reliability course at North Carolina State University has a learning objective of using appropriate testing techniques for the development of a reliable and secure system. Beginning in Fall 2005, the semester project has involved the development and testing of the open source and freely-available iTrust Medical Records system prototype. Our vision is to build a community of educators, students, and medical professionals that can collaborate and use the iTrust project as a development platform and testbed for secure and reliable application development.</p>		CE4	Resumo.